

Is a (satellite) image worth a thousand data points?

Comparing machine learning approaches for predicting social and environmental inequalities across England.

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Summary

This work explores the use of satellite imagery for predicting inequalities, with a focus on air quality and house prices in England. We employed three approaches for making predictions: one based on urban characteristics, another solely using image embeddings, and a third combining both methods. Initial findings indicate that incorporating image embeddings had limited impact on prediction accuracy, especially for house prices. However, satellite image embeddings alone displayed promising predictive potential, suggesting their relevance, particularly when scaled to cover the entire country. This study underscores the viability of satellite images as standalone predictors or enhancements to geospatial machine learning models.

KEYWORDS: AI, machine learning, remote sensing, urban inequalities, geospatial modelling

1 Background

Urban areas globally face social and environmental inequalities, exhibiting multifaceted and spatially diverse patterns over time. Understanding and analysing these heterogeneous data can be challenging, mostly because the data that captures environmental variation and dynamics are high dimensional and need to be measured at high temporal and spatial resolution. Recent advances in high-throughput computing have revealed the potential of using images to analyse complex urban environments, which provide new opportunities for studying cities (8; 1; 6). Particularly, remotely

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sensed images offer valuable insights (14; 7; 13). Recent efforts have focused on developing generalisable models, including foundation models and large vision transformers, capable of predicting socioeconomic or environmental outcomes using satellite images (9; 12).

Here we present work that extends The Alan Turing Institute’s DemoLand project¹. DemoLand provides a tool designed to assess the effect of competing aspects of land use on a variety of indicators relevant for policy. The tool serves as a resource for those involved in urban planning and decision-making, offering a comprehensive overview of the impacts of land use policy through the development of scenarios. Users can compare and analyse the baseline conditions with the outcomes of specific scenarios, facilitating informed decision-making for sustainable urban development.

Our current model integrates geospatial variables such as demographic data, land use information, and details on urban form and function. Gathering these variables involves data extraction from various sources, which is a time-intensive process. To enhance our model’s efficiency and explore new analytical capabilities, we are considering the integration of satellite imagery. This approach employs modern computer vision techniques, including vision transformers, to create image representations (embeddings). The goal is to assess the potential of using satellite images either independently or in conjunction with traditional data sources to model urban inequalities across the country. The outcomes have significance beyond our project; they extend to the broader geospatial modelling community, notably as satellite imagery and computing power become increasingly accessible. This underscores the growing potential of integrating image data into traditional geospatial models.

The extended abstract includes the preliminary results of the analysis, which includes only the city of Newcastle upon Tyne, however, the final presentation will include results across England.

2 Data

2.1 Satellite images

We use the satellite composite dataset as detailed in Corbane et al. (4). This dataset comprises a global, cloud-free pixel-based image composite generated from Sentinel-2 data. Since the level of analysis is done on a H3 (level 9) spatial scale (11), we explore two distinct preprocessing methods to fuse the hexagonal geometries from H3 with the imagery’s square grid. The composite images are segmented into chips, each measuring approximately 420×420 pixels. Additionally, we introduce a masking step in the preprocessing, where each chip is accompanied by a H3 mask. To ensure consistency², we aggregate individual masks into a universal mask (Figure 1, right), applied uniformly across all image tiles. Figure 1 illustrates a specific H3 mask for a tile and the resulting summed masks for the entire dataset.

¹<https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/research-projects/demoland>

²Due to the Earth’s curvature, H3 masks exhibit varying shapes across regions of England. Although these differences in H3 masks are minor in practice, they could be detected by the AI model, potentially allowing it to infer the geographic location of an image. To address this variability, we developed uniform masks to standardise the representation across all areas.

Figure 1: From left to right: The first image tile represents the unmasked tile, the middle tile represents the H3 mask of that specific location, and the right mask is the summed mask over the whole dataset.

2.2 Urban predictors

We use a set of 59 predictor variables³ that include information on land cover, population density, urban form and function, as well as morphology (5). We further use latitude and longitude in the model as predictors. More details on the project homepage.

2.3 Outcome variables

We use two indicators, air quality and house prices, to measure urban inequality. Our air quality index combines PM2.5, PM10, NO2, and SO2 data from the UK AIR project by DEFRA⁴, presented on a 1 km grid. House price data is sourced from (3), covering 2018–2019 and calculated as mean price per sqm per output area. Due to the data not being fully current, our modelling results are presented as percentage changes from the baseline. More details on data acquisition and preprocessing are available on the project homepage⁵.

3 Methods

Figure 2 shows an overview of the three different approaches. In the first approach, we use 59 urban features, as mentioned in Section 2.2, to predict the urban inequalities. In approach B, we use satellite image embeddings (feature vector) to make the predictions. Lastly, we combine the two datasets to predict air quality and house prices.

³<https://urban-analytics-technology-platform.github.io/demoland-project/book/method.html#variable-pruning-and-final-variable-set>

⁴<https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/gis-licences>

⁵<https://urban-analytics-technology-platform.github.io/demoland-project/book/method.html>

Figure 2: Overview of the modelling approaches. The feature vector refers to the satellite image embeddings extracted from the vision transformer. The preliminary results refer to Newcastle, however, the final results presented will be reported on England.

3.1 Image embeddings

We use the SatlasPretrain with Swin Transformer backbone model to create satellite image embeddings. The model was trained on Landsat and Sentinel-2 images (with 10m resolution). It covers 302M labels under 137 categories and seven label types (2). The embeddings include four positional encodings, which we flatten into one feature vector per image. The extracted feature vector is very high-dimensional ($n \times 2,704,256$) and in order to be suitable for further machine learning methods ($n > p$), we apply a principal component analysis (PCA) to the image embeddings to extract the first 1000 principal components to be added as features. These represent about 75% of the variance of the embeddings.

3.2 Regression model

We use a histogram-based gradient boosting regression tree as classifier as implemented by the ML python library scikit-learn (Sklearn) to predict either air pollution or house prices across the study area. In order to capture the spatial characteristics of the indicators, we augment our dataset with an additional 59 features, representing the spatial lag of the original set. The lag is computed as the mean value of the variable within a neighbourhood, whose definition is established empirically. Preliminary experiments showed best performance with contiguity of order 5 as most effective definition of spatial lag.

4 Preliminary results

The preliminary results, detailed in Tables 1 and 2, provide insights into the performance of modelling strategies for predicting air quality and house prices. It is essential to note that these results are specific to the city of Newcastle upon Tyne. However, we intend to extend our analysis to encompass all of England, for which we will have results in time of GISRUK. Data and code will be made available with the England results in time for the conference.

	H3 mask	MSE	ME	R^2
A. Other variables	-	0.667204	0.647141	0.806953
B. Embeddings	no	1.612550	1.046995	0.439548
B. Embeddings	yes	1.474187	0.977540	0.590063
C. Embeddings + other variables	no	1.034425	0.820467	0.651827
C. Embeddings + other variables	yes	0.876462	0.744428	0.743717

Table 1: Air quality model; averages across 5 folds.

	H3 mask	MSE	ME	R^2
A. Other variables	-	0.074757	0.209343	0.273205
B. Embeddings	no	0.116595	0.271397	0.091183
B. Embeddings	yes	0.107899	0.261851	0.041302
C. Embeddings + other variables	no	0.113382	0.263540	0.046359
C. Embeddings + other variables	yes	0.093844	0.244408	0.092326

Table 2: House price model; averages across 5 folds.

In the air quality model, using only urban variables (without image embeddings) achieved the highest performance. Conversely, relying solely on embeddings resulted in the poorest air pollution predictions. Notably, using only image information accounted for about 75 percent of the 59 urban features in combination with information on latitude and longitude. While not fully competitive, the result looks promising, especially given the fact that the model is only tested in Newcastle upon Tyne and scaling the analysis to the whole of England will allow the model to learn more diverse patterns to make predictions from. Approach C did not reach the accuracy of approach A, which could indicate overfitting due to a high number of predictor variables in comparison to observations. House prices were overall a lot more difficult to predict. The results were not satisfactory, which warrants further investigation. For both air quality and house prices, the introduction of the H3 mask slightly improved model performance.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, the use of remote sensing and increased computational capabilities holds promise for urban analysis. We compared various approaches for predicting urban inequalities, focusing on air pollution and house prices in Newcastle. Our findings suggest that incorporating image embeddings does not currently improve prediction accuracy, potentially due to dataset size. Our next steps

Figure 3: Results of air quality regression model over 5 folds.

involve expanding the model to cover all of England, as initial experiments indicate potential for better results. Additionally, we plan to fine-tune a vision transformer model directly to improve prediction accuracy with satellite images.

Figure 4: Results of house price regression model over 5 folds.

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7 Biographies

7.1 Antje Barbara Metzler

Antje Barbara Metzler is a Research Associate with the Science of Cities and Regions group at the Alan Turing Institute and holds a PhD from Imperial College London. Her research focuses on leveraging deep learning techniques and satellite imagery to enhance traditional data and models for understanding urban areas.

7.2 Martin Fleischmann

Martin Fleischmann a researcher in urban morphology and geographic data science based at Charles University focusing on quantitative analysis and classification of cities, remote sensing, and bits of AI. While not doing the research, I write open source software, promote open science and help others with their data.

7.3 Anna Zanchetta

Anna is a Turing Research Fellow at the Alan Turing Institute, where she investigates the use of AI for semi-automated building footprints detection in collaboration with HOT (Humanitarian Openstreetmap Team). She is interested in open source geospatial tools applied to sustainability, environmental and urban studies.

7.4 Jon Yong

Jonathan Yong is a Research Data Scientist at The Alan Turing Institute. A graduate of the University of Oxford (MChem and DPhil), Jon has been working to develop reproducible and robust scientific software, and has a particular interest in the theory and applications of functional programming.

7.5 Stuart Lynn

Dr Stuart Lynn is Research Data Scientist with the Science of Cities and Regions group at the Alan Turing institute. His interests involve widening the participation in scientific and political inquiry to non-traditional communities through the development of tools, data and processes that promote active participation and decision making.

7.6 Dani Arribas-Bel

Dani Arribas-Bel is Professor in Geographic Data Science at the the University of Liverpool, and Deputy Programme Director for Urban Analytics at the Alan Turing Institute. His research combines modern computation with new forms of data to shed light on the spatial structure(s) of cities.

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